

Blended Learning: The Future of Indian Higher Education through the Lens of National Education Policy–2020

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Blended learning has emerged as a transformative approach in the realm of higher education, particularly in the context of India's evolving educational landscape. With the advent of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, there has been a renewed emphasis on integrating technology and traditional pedagogical methods to enhance the quality and accessibility of education. This innovative blend of online and face-to-face learning experiences not only caters to the diverse learning needs of students but also fosters a more interactive and personalized learning environment. As India strives to address the challenges of expanding higher education access, improving educational outcomes, and promoting lifelong learning, blended learning stands out as a crucial strategy that aligns with the goals and aspirations outlined in the NEP 2020. This introduction sets the stage for exploring the significance of blended learning as the need of the hour for higher education in India, while also highlighting its synergy with the transformative vision of the National Education Policy 2020 (Das & Barman, 2023).

Numerous reforms were proposed for all educational levels, including higher education, in the National Education Policy 2020 (NEP). NEP-2020 places a strong focus on integrating technology into all phases and procedures of education. In order to guarantee equal chances for all students, it promotes utilizing technology in a variety of educational processes, such as admissions, examinations, evaluations, and recruiting. Furthermore, NEP-2020 seeks to raise the Gross Enrollment Ratio in higher education which includes vocational education from 26.3% in 2018 to 50% by 2035 (Aisha & Ratra, 2023).

The adoption and distribution of technology across stakeholders would not be consistent in

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India due to the country's enormous geographical expanses, socio-cultural variety, and disparities in economic background among pupils. The National Education Policy (NEP) promotes blended learning's incorporation into higher education. This method is intended to be used nationwide and in a variety of academic fields. In addition to analysing the changing patterns of blended learning in this setting, the goal of this study is to investigate the major points of the NEP 2020 on blended learning in Indian higher education. The study also aims to identify possible problems and challenges that the Indian higher education system may run into while attempting to integrate blended learning (Sharma et al., 2022).

The aim of the present study is to highlight the characteristics of blended learning through the lens of NEP 2020. It also highlights the emerging trends of blended learning in higher education and the challenges of blended learning.

Higher Education and National Education Policy–2020

The National Education Policy aims to prioritize the identification and nurturing of individual student talents, encouraging critical and creative thinking to enhance decision-making and innovation. Technology is seen as pivotal in both teaching and learning, addressing educational management challenges and language barriers. The policy emphasizes the value of research alongside training and implementation efforts, with the overarching goal of raising educational standards in India (Kathi et al., 2022).

Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs provided by institutions like the National Institute of Open Schooling (NIOS) and State Open Schools will utilize technology to reach students unable to access traditional schooling. Teaching methods will shift towards competency-based approaches to improve learning outcomes. Language instruction will incorporate gamification, apps, and cultural elements such as films and music. Additionally, there's a

vision for Indian colleges to establish international campuses and for globally renowned universities to operate within India (Das & Das, 2024).

Special efforts will be made to support students from socially and economically disadvantaged backgrounds, with a focus on developing innovative courses and improving academic performance. Mathematics and computational thinking will receive particular attention due to their importance in AI-driven job roles. The policy underscores the role of higher education in fostering innovation and knowledge creation to stimulate economic growth (Lata et al., 2022).

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) will establish support systems and competitions to promote student innovation. Faculty members will be empowered to initiate new teaching, research, and service projects, fostering creativity within institutions. Experimentation with teaching methods within an innovative higher education framework will be encouraged, with a focus on supporting technical education and innovation in technical sectors (Shukla et al., 2022).

The National Educational Technology forum (NETF), an independent entity, will facilitate the exchange of ideas and technological advancements to enhance education delivery from secondary to higher levels. The policy recognizes the necessity for alternative educational methods highlighted by the COVID-19 pandemic and stresses the importance of bridging the digital divide. It proposes initiatives such as online education pilot programs, digital infrastructure development, and content creation (Gupta & Choubey, 2021).

Looking ahead to 2030, interdisciplinary colleges and universities will have a more significant role in teacher education. A four-year integrated B.Ed degree will become the minimum qualification for teachers, granting them more autonomy in selecting teaching methods suited to their students. The policy underscores the importance of socio-emotional learning and continuous professional development for teachers through workshops and online courses (Saxena, 2020).

Research and innovation in education are seen as making systems more adaptable and inclusive. Teachers are encouraged to employ creative methods to engage students, thereby enhancing critical

thinking and problem-solving skills. The policy underscores the importance of motivated teachers in driving educational innovation, emphasizing self-motivation in research and educational advancements (Kumar, 2022).

Rising Patterns of Blended Learning in Higher Education

Blended learning has a rich history in Indian higher education, originating from the incorporation of technology into educational environments, notably in the Open and Distance Learning (ODL) system. This evolution, spanning from traditional correspondence education to contemporary online and blended learning, requires further investigation. While the National Education Policy of 2020 brought attention to blended learning, its practical adoption surged during the COVID-19 pandemic. With government-mandated lockdowns shuttering educational institutions, online learning became crucial, bridging the technological gap (Kaurav et al., 2021). Pre-pandemic, face-to-face learning was predominant, but the abrupt shift to online learning during COVID-19 was unprecedented. Now, a blend of online and face-to-face learning is termed the “new normal,” shaping preferences, habits, and teaching methodologies. This integration, known as blended learning, offers students the advantages of both personal interactions and digital resources, equipping them for the demands of the 21st century and fueled further by the National Education Policy of 2020.

Blended learning, a pedagogical approach that combines traditional face-to-face classroom teaching with online learning, is gaining traction in Indian higher education. This hybrid model offers flexibility, personalized learning experiences, and opportunities for collaborative and interactive learning. Here are some rising patterns of blended learning in Indian higher education:

Flexible Learning Paths

With the integration of online components, students have the flexibility to learn at their own pace and convenience. This asynchronous learning mode allows students to access course materials, lectures, and resources anytime, anywhere, which is especially beneficial for working professionals and those with other commitments (Kožuško et al., 2013).

Technology Integration

The adoption of Learning Management Systems (LMS) like Moodle, Blackboard, and Google Classroom has become more prevalent. These platforms facilitate course management, content delivery, assessments, and communication between students and educators. Additionally, the use of educational apps, multimedia resources, and interactive simulations enhances the learning experience and caters to diverse learning styles (Kanwal et al., 2023).

Personalized Learning

Blended learning enables educators to leverage data analytics and learning analytics to track student progress, identify learning gaps, and tailor instruction to meet individual needs. Adaptive learning technologies, which adjust content and difficulty based on student performance and feedback, are also being integrated to provide personalized learning pathways (Khasawneh, 2023).

Collaborative Learning Opportunities

The blended learning environment encourages collaborative learning through discussion forums, group projects, and peer interactions both online and offline. Virtual classrooms and online collaboration tools enable students to engage with peers from different locations, fostering a sense of community and enhancing teamwork and communication skills.

Professional Development for Educators

To effectively implement blended learning strategies, there is a growing emphasis on professional development programs and training for educators. Institutions are investing in workshops, seminars, and online courses to equip faculty with the necessary skills and knowledge to design, deliver, and evaluate blended learning experiences effectively.

Hybrid Course Models

Universities and colleges are increasingly offering hybrid courses that combine online and face-to-face instruction in a structured manner. This blended approach allows for a balance between traditional classroom teaching and online learning activities, optimizing the use of resources and providing a richer and more engaging learning experience for students.

Assessment and Feedback Mechanisms

With the shift towards blended learning, there is a need for innovative assessment and feedback mechanisms that align with the blended learning environment. Formative assessments, online quizzes, peer reviews, and self-assessment tools are being utilized to evaluate student learning outcomes and provide timely and constructive feedback.

Accessibility and Inclusivity

Blended learning promotes accessibility and inclusivity by accommodating diverse learning needs and preferences. Institutions are focusing on creating accessible digital content, providing assistive technologies, and implementing inclusive design principles to ensure that all students, including those with disabilities, can fully participate and succeed in blended learning environments.

Blended learning is reshaping the landscape of higher education in India by offering a flexible, personalized, and collaborative learning experience. As technology continues to evolve and educators embrace innovative pedagogical approaches, the adoption and integration of blended learning are expected to grow, driving positive educational outcomes and enhancing the overall quality of higher education in the country.

Challenges of Blended Learning in Indian Higher Education

Blended learning models present several significant obstacles, such as the costs associated with technology, insufficient training, technical glitches, the necessity to tailor content for blended formats, diminished student-teacher relationships, reduced learner retention, inadequate infrastructure, a shortage of digital devices, unreliable internet connectivity, elevated internet expenses, challenges in affording and managing digital tools, reluctance to engage online, difficulty in overseeing and managing workloads in blended settings, a lack of pertinent technical resources, and feelings of anxiety. Additionally, these challenges encompass the diverse backgrounds and learning requirements of students, the time commitment and pace of learning, student availability, and their ability to adapt to course content and employ technology innovatively.

Blended learning offers numerous benefits such as flexibility, personalized learning experiences,

and increased accessibility, it also comes with its set of challenges, particularly in the context of higher education in India. Here are some of the key challenges faced by higher education institutions in India when implementing blended learning:

Infrastructure and Technology Readiness

One of the primary challenges is the lack of adequate technological infrastructure and resources in many higher education institutions in India. Reliable internet connectivity, access to computers or tablets, and software platforms conducive to online learning are often lacking, particularly in rural areas. This digital divide can hinder the effective implementation of blended learning.

Faculty Training and Preparedness

For blended learning to be successful, faculty members need to be adequately trained in online teaching methodologies, instructional design, and the use of educational technology tools. However, there is often a lack of professional development opportunities and resistance to change among faculty members, which can impede the adoption of blended learning (Gedik et al., 2012).

Quality Assurance and Standardization

Ensuring the quality and standardization of blended learning courses can be challenging. There is a need for robust mechanisms to evaluate and monitor the effectiveness of blended learning programs, maintain academic rigour, and ensure that learning outcomes are met. Without proper quality assurance measures, there is a risk of compromising the quality of education (Dridi et al., 2020).

Student Engagement and Motivation

Keeping students engaged and motivated in a blended learning environment can be challenging, especially when they have to juggle multiple responsibilities and distractions outside the classroom. Effective strategies and interactive learning materials need to be developed to enhance student engagement and foster a sense of community and collaboration among students (Ashraf, et. al., 2022).

Accessibility and Inclusivity

While blended learning aims to increase accessibility to education, it can inadvertently create barriers for students with disabilities or

those from marginalized backgrounds. Institutions need to ensure that their blended learning platforms and materials are accessible to all students, including those with special needs, and that they do not exacerbate existing inequalities in education (Namyssova, et. al., 2019).

Cost Implications

Implementing and maintaining a blended learning infrastructure can be costly, requiring investments in technology, software licenses, faculty training, and ongoing support services. Higher education institutions in India, many of which operate on limited budgets, may find it challenging to allocate sufficient funds for these purposes.

Cultural and Pedagogical Challenges

The traditional pedagogical methods prevalent in Indian higher education, which emphasize rote learning and teacher-centred instruction, may not align well with the interactive and student-centred approach promoted in blended learning. Additionally, cultural attitudes towards technology and online education may vary, with some stakeholders being more resistant to the adoption of blended learning methods (Muhria, et. al., 2023).

While blended learning holds great promise for transforming higher education in India by making it more flexible, inclusive, and learner-centred, its successful implementation requires addressing these multifaceted challenges effectively. Collaborative efforts involving policymakers, educational institutions, faculty members, students, and other stakeholders are essential to overcoming these challenges and harnessing the full potential of blended learning in higher education in India.

Discussion and Conclusion

The world's rapid advancement affects many sectors, including education, which is crucial to global development. Today, technology has a significant impact on learning methods, augmenting traditional teaching with tech-based components to make them more engaging, effective, and long-lasting to achieve desired educational outcomes. The NEP-2020 recognizes the growing significance of digital technologies in education and supports blended learning, which holds the potential to offer a variety of courses and training. The NEP-2020 envisions curriculum innovations that can transform

higher education in India by wisely integrating technology. This approach can facilitate blended learning programs that promote sustainability in education.

When properly organized, taking into account a variety of aspects such as instructional techniques, educator and learner abilities, infrastructure, and intended learning outcomes, blended learning solves gaps and improves higher education. Blended learning can yield outcomes that are more effective when combined properly. NEP-2020 promotes balanced mixes and combinations of digital and in-person learning, highlighting the value of both. Multiple models that may be customized as needed and are adaptive to topic or content requirements are provided by blended learning. To do this, policymakers, educators, course developers, and socio-cultural and economic specialists must work together to create a variety of blended learning methodologies that take into account the needs of learners, topic requirements, and sociocultural and economic variables. Learner satisfaction and learning results can be improved by using well-designed mixes and apps in courses (Das, et. al., 2023).

Blended learning emerges as a pivotal strategy in the contemporary landscape of higher education in India, aligning seamlessly with the objectives and vision outlined in the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. The multifaceted benefits of blended learning, ranging from enhanced accessibility and flexibility to fostering self-directed learning and critical thinking, make it a need of the hour for higher educational institutions across the country.

NEP 2020's emphasis on holistic, multidisciplinary, and flexible education resonates with the core principles of blended learning. By integrating traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning modalities, institutions can cater to diverse learning styles and bridge the educational divide, ensuring equitable access to quality education for all. Furthermore, the technological integration inherent in blended learning aligns with NEP 2020's vision of leveraging technology to improve educational outcomes and promote lifelong learning.

In conclusion, the adoption and implementation of blended learning in higher education institutions in India can serve as a catalyst for transformative change, fostering innovation, inclusivity, and

excellence in alignment with the aspirations of the National Education Policy–2020. Embracing this paradigm shift will not only enhance the quality and relevance of higher education but also empower learners to thrive in an increasingly interconnected and dynamic global landscape.

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